

Subrogation in Islamic and Conventional Financial Institutions: Library Research and VOSviewer Bibliometrics

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Abstract

This research aims to map research topics surrounding Subrogation in Islamic and Conventional Financial Institutions using a qualitative approach, which is in the nature of a library research. The data collection technique is: first, open the Perish/Harzing software, then search for journals based on the title words category with the key word " Subrogation to Islamic and Conventional Financial Institutions " within the entire year period. Second, collect journal title data in Microsoft Excel, and identify duplicate journal titles. Third, download files in RIS (Research Information Systems) and PDF (Portable Document Format) format from all journals for which data has been collected. Fourth, enter the RIS data file into Mendeley software Desktop. Data analysis technique by mapping research topics around Subrogation in Islamic and Conventional Financial Institutions based on the journals that have been collected. The research results show that there are 13 mappings and 30 research topics using literature studies regarding Subrogation in Islamic and Conventional Financial Institutions. The implication and contribution of this research is the mapping of research topics surrounding subrogation in Islamic and Conventional Financial Institutions, both frequently and rarely researched by researchers, so that other researchers can find out the research gaps in this topic.

Keywords: Subrogation; Islamic and Conventional Financial Institutions; Library Research; Bibliometrics; VOSviewer

Introduction

Every human being cannot be separated from transaction activities, one of which is credit. However, there are several methods in credit that may still be rarely known, namely "Subrogation". Subrogation is the replacement of rights by a third party who pays the creditor to fulfill its debt payment obligations. The creditor can only confiscate the collateral apart from the customer's summons. Material collateral can be written off not only between creditors and debtors, but also between creditors and third parties who guarantee the debtor's implementation of obligations. (Komang O, Ni N, Sukerti N, 2017).

In the current era, credit is one of the sharia banking products that is in great demand by the public. One way to pay this credit can be done using subrogation. Subrogation is regulated in Article 1400 of the Civil Code concerning subrogation, which discusses the replacement of rights by third parties who pay creditors. The transfer must be stated clearly, because the transfer is different from the repayment of the debt. The purpose of third party payments to creditors is to replace the old creditor's position, not to release the debt from the obligation to pay the creditor (Naki, 2019).

Based on searches via the Garuda website (Garda Reference Digital), many researchers have conducted research on subrogation. There were 28 subrogation studies from 2014-2022. In several studies, researchers discuss

subrogation in companies in conjunction with applicable laws. There are differences between this research and previous research, this research discusses mapping research around subrogation in Islamic and Conventional Financial Institutions which has not previously been discussed.

The aim of this research is to map research topics surrounding subrogation use library research (library research). The difference between this research and previous research is that this research explains all research topics surrounding subrogation, so that it can be a reference for other researchers. The implication and contribution of this research is mapping research topics around subrogation, both those that are often or rarely researched by researchers, so that other researchers can find out the gaps in research on this topic.

Literature Review

As explained in the Civil Code Article 1400, subrogation is the transfer of a creditor's position by a third party in exchange for agreed remuneration or as required by law.(Huda, 2022).

Sharia financial inclusion refers to efforts to ensure that all individuals and economic entities, regardless of their economic, social, or geographic background, have fair and appropriate access to financial products and services that comply with sharia principles. Sharia principles are Islamic economic rules and guidelines that prohibit riba (interest), excessive speculation, and investment in businesses that are forbidden under Islamic law. Sharia financial inclusion includes a variety of financial products and services, such as savings, microfinance, insurance, investment and other financial instruments, that comply with sharia principles. The aim of sharia financial inclusion is to increase public access to financial services that are in accordance with the values and principles of the Islamic religion. Sharia financial inclusion has a positive impact on the economy, including reducing poverty, improving community welfare, and strengthening financial system stability. Apart from that, sharia financial inclusion also supports the development of the sharia financial sector as a whole, which involves financial institutions such as sharia banks, sharia insurance companies and sharia capital markets.

Library research is a type of research that focuses on the analysis, understanding and synthesis of existing literature in a particular field of knowledge or topic. The aim of literature study research is to identify the latest developments, weaknesses, strengths, findings and trends in the relevant research field. In contrast to experimental research or field research, literature study research does not involve collecting primary data through observation, interviews, or experiments. Instead, researchers collect data from secondary sources such as books, scientific journals, articles and other academic documents. After collecting data, researchers then analyze, compare, and organize the literature to achieve a deeper understanding of the topic under study.

Bibliometric studies are a research method used to analyze and measure scientific publications in a particular field, using quantitative data. In bibliometric studies, the data analyzed includes information about the number of publications, authors, subjects, publication sources, citations, and impact factor. The goal of bibliometric studies is to provide an overview of trends and patterns in scientific publications, as well as measure the impact of these publications on the academic community and industry. Bibliometric studies can be used to identify emerging research areas, measure research performance,

and compare performance between researchers, institutions, or countries. Bibliometric studies are usually carried out using bibliometric software, such as Web of Science, Scopus, or Google Scholar. Bibliometric methods can also be used to conduct qualitative analysis, such as content analysis or other qualitative analysis, to understand the issues expressed in certain scientific publications (Dubyna et al., 2022) .

VOSviewer is open source software used in bibliometric studies to visualize and analyze the network of links between documents or scientific publications. VOSviewer can be used to analyze bibliometric data collected from various sources, such as Scopus, Web of Science, or Google Scholar. VOSviewer can be used to perform quantitative and qualitative analysis, such as cluster identification, citation analysis, and topic mapping. In cluster analysis, VOSviewer can group scientific publications into similar groups based on their association with a particular topic. Citation analysis can be used to identify the most cited scientific publications in a research field. Topic mapping can be used to identify the most widely discussed research topics in a field. One of the advantages of VOSviewer is its ability to produce attractive and easy-to-understand visualizations, such as heatmaps, network graphs and topic trees. This visualization can help researchers understand patterns and trends in bibliometric data more easily and quickly. VOSviewer can be used by researchers, academics, and practitioners in various research fields, including social science, information science, health, and information technology (van Eck NJ, 2022) .

Methodology

This research uses research methods with a mix-method approach, namely quantitative methods in bibliometric studies and qualitative methods in library research. The object of the research is Subrogation in Islamic and Conventional Financial Institutions. The type of data used is secondary data. The scope of the data used is scientific publication articles about Subrogation which comes from national and accredited journals. The source of data collection comes from the Garuda website (Digital Reference Garba). Data analysis tools are Microsoft Excel, Mendeley Desktop, VOSviewer, and Perish software.

Data collection techniques include: (1) visiting the Garuda website and Perish software, then search for journal titles based on the title words category with the keyword " Subrogation " for the entire year (2014-2022); (2) collect journal title data in Microsoft Excel, and identify duplicate journal titles; (3) download files in RIS (Research Information Systems) and PDF (Portable Document Format) formats from all journals for which data has been collected; and (4) inserting the RIS data file into Mendeley Desktop software.

Data analysis techniques include: (1) mapping RIS data files on Mendeley Desktop based on year, author and publisher; (2) mapping the results of bibliometric network visualization and scientific publication trends using the VOSviewer (Visualization of Similarities) algorithm software based on the number of clusters and items; and (3) map topics, methods, research findings, and research space based on library research. (Budianto, 2022) .

Results and Discussion

4.1. Mapping the Distribution of Scientific Publications Regarding Subrogation in Islamic and Conventional Financial Institutions

Search results of research publications on subrogation in Islamic and conventional financial institutions from 2014 to 2022 show an increase in the number of publications every year, especially in the last five years. From the information obtained, there are 25 article titles in accredited national journals that discuss subrogation. Thus, an average of more than five scientific publications on subrogation are published each year.

Table 1. Scientific publication data regarding Subrogation by year

Year of Publication	Number of published articles	Year of Publication	Number of published articles
2014	1	2019	3
2015	1	2020	5
2017	4	2021	5
2018	5	2022	1
Total: 25 _			

Source: Processed data, Microsoft Excel 2016.

In table 2, there are 3 affiliates/institutions that publish the most research articles regarding Subrogation in Islamic and Conventional Financial Institutions.

Table 2. Scientific journal publishing institutions regarding Subrogation

Name of Affiliate/Institution	Number of Publications
Collection of Law Faculty Student Journals, Lex Privatum, Solutions	2
Acta Diurnal, Al Qodiri: Journal of Education, Social and Religious, Economic Development Law, Prima Legal Science (IHP), Indonesia, Indonesian Notary, Cahaya Perempuan Journal, Legal Science Journal, Udayana Master of Law Journal, Student Online Journal (JOM) Field of Legal Studies, Tambusai Education Journal, Journal of Applied Accounting Research, Kertha Negara: Journal of Legal Studies, Kertha Semaya: Journal of Legal Sciences, Lex Renaissance, Legal Reform, Seiko: Journal of Management & Business, Sign Jurnal Hukum, Uir Law Review	1
(Budianto, 2022) (Budianto, 2022) (Budianto & Dewi, 2022) (Rohimah et al., 2023) (Budianto, 2023) (Budianto & Dewi, 2023) (Dewi et al., 2023) (Budianto & Dewi, 2023) (Budianto & Dewi, 2023) (Budianto, 2023) (Budianto, 2023) (Rohmandika et al., 2023) (Budianto & Dewi, 2023) (Emiliani et al., 2023) (Budianto & Dewi, 2023) (Budianto, 2023) (Budianto, Saputra, et al., 2023) (Gozali et al., 2023) (Rofika et al., 2023) (Budianto, Dewi, et al., 2023) (Budianto & Dewi, 2023) (Zahro et al., 2023) (Budianto & Dewi, 2023) (Budianto & Dewi, 2023) (Budianto & Dewi, 2023) (Rahmawati et al., 2023) (Shalsabila et al., 2023) (Fitriawati et al., 2023) (Budianto & Dewi, 2023) (Febrian & Budianto, 2023) (Rohmah et al., 2023) (Budianto & Dewi, 2023)	

Source: Processed data, Microsoft Excel 2016.

Furthermore, all researchers only wrote 1 journal article about Subrogation in Islamic and Conventional Financial Institutions. They are Yoga Arief Setiawan, Yeni Salma Barlinti, Lucy Margareth Napitupulu (University of North Sumatra), Winardi Mamonto, Luh Made Asri Dwi Lestari (Udayana University), Anak Agung Gede Duwira Hadi Santosa (Udayana University), Moh. Luthfi Mahrus (STAN State Finance Polytechnic), Muhadi Prabowo (STAN State Financial Polytechnic), Nur Aisyah Kustiani (STAN State Financial Polytechnic), Rihandy (IBLAM School of Law), Misbahul Huda (IBLAM School of Law), Yuwita (Syiah Kuala University), Amiruddin Abdul Wahab (Syiah Kuala University), Mahfud (Syiah Kuala University), Yunesha Ratih Fitriani (Indonesian Islamic University), Suhaila Zulkifli (Prima Indonesia University), Luthvia Meidina (Prima Indonesia University), Shalihin Hernata Dhalimunthe (Prima Indonesia University), Intan Carolyn Ginting (Prima Indonesia University), Asuan (Palembang University), Abdul Rahman (Sebelas Maret University), Ibnu Fadhli (Andalas University), Fany Alfarisi (Andalas University), Aristya Hadinata (Udayana University), Ida Ayu Sukihana (Udayana University), Afni Syafitri (Riau University), Selvi Harvia Santri, Ananda Dara Prameswaria (Padjadjaran University), Man S Sastrawidjaja (Padjadjaran University), R. Kartikasari (Padjadjaran University), Rhezar Adinanda Putra (Surabaya University), Marsidah (Palembang University), Astika Rahma Yustisia (Brawijaya University), Iwan Permadi (Brawijaya University), Itta Andrijani (Brawijaya University), Cecep Supriyatna, Anwar Ma'rufi (STAI An-Nawawi), Agus Riyanto (Putera Batam University), Ni Komang Nopitayuni (Udayana University), Ni Nyoman Sukerti (University Udayana), and Jifer Naki.

4.2. Bibliometric Mapping of Research Regarding Subrogation in Islamic and Conventional Financial Institutions

Search results for research articles on the Garuda website (Digital Reference Garba) are exported in RIS (Research Information Systems) format, then entered and analyzed using VOSViewer. The results are as follows:

Network visualization of research development maps regarding Subrogation in Islamic and Conventional Financial Institutions

Data was processed using VOSViewer 1.6.18 software.

co-word map network visualization of research developments regarding Subrogation in Islamic and Conventional Financial Institutions are divided into 7 clusters and 83 topics, as follows:

- Cluster 1. The color red consists of 24 topics, namely: accident, according, compensation, credit, credit recovery, data, double benefit, implementation, insurance policy, interview, law, literature, principle, problem, research data, secondary data, solution, study, subrogation, subrogation process, subrogation provision, third party, time, transportation agreement.
- Cluster 2. The green color consists of 14 topics, namely: bank, contract, credit agreement, credit facility, credit settlement, creditor, empirical method, guarantee, guarantee institution, legal protection, guarantee institution, overview, payment, process.
- Cluster 3. Dark blue consists of 13 topics, namely: based on sharia principles, debtors, debtors from the time the claim is paid, using juridical research methods, civil code, this research uses, third parties, standards, subrogation, years, regarding sharia financial institutions, credit guarantees, legal efforts to rescue collateral belonging to third parties in the event that the debtor defaults.
- Cluster 4. The yellow color consists of 10 topics, namely: business credit, collateral, debt, debtor, effort, new creditor, obligation, old creditor, repayment, transition.
- Cluster 5. Purple consists of 10 topics, namely: application, civil code, customer debtor, legal consequence, loan, loan agreement, loan takeover, mortgage right, provision, provision son subrogation.
- Cluster 6. Light blue consists of 6 topics, namely: assets, guarantee company assets, influence, claim risk, individually significant to returns, subrogation and investment results opinion to returns.
- Cluster 7. Orange consists of 6 topics, namely: analogy method, borgtocht, guarantee agreement, guarantor, regulation, subrogation right.

Mapping Research Topics using Library Research regarding Subrogation in Islamic and Conventional Financial Institutions

Library Research study in previous research journals, the researchers found 13 topics related to Subrogation in Islamic and Conventional Financial Institutions, namely:

First, subrogation in motor vehicle insurance agreements, based on the commercial law book, and assistance in settling claims.

Second, subrogation as legal protection for banks in resolving credit defaults.

Third, subrogation in the transfer of land rights using lastgeving.

Fourth, the notary's responsibility in making a subrogation agreement.

Fifth, violation of subrogation rights.

Sixth, subrogation as a transfer of mortgage rights according to Law no. 4 of 1996.

Seventh, the application of subrogation to insurance companies according to insurance law studies, from a justice perspective.

Eighth, the application of subrogation to the distribution of People's Business Credit/KUR according to civil law.

Ninth, legal certainty of subrogation rights of sharia guarantee companies for financing written -off by sharia banks.

Tenth, the use of subrogation deeds in the context of implementing Article 2 of Aceh Qanun Number 11 of 2018 concerning Sharia Financial Institutions.

Eleventh, recording subrogated receivables from the guarantee company.

Twelfth, the effect of subrogation on profitability.

Thirteenth, subrogation is one of the reasons for annulling an agreement according to the civil code.

The following are the titles of the research topics:

- IMPLEMENTATION OF THE PRINCIPLE OF SUBROGATION IN MOTOR VEHICLE INSURANCE AGREEMENTS (A study in Banda Aceh City)
- LEGAL PROTECTION FOR BANK IN SETTLEMENT OF CREDIT DUE TO DEFECTS THROUGH SUBROGATION (Study at PT. Bank Pembangunan Daerah Jawa Timur Tbk Kediri Branch)
- SUBROGATION AS A LEGAL REMEDY TO RESCUE SECURITY OBJECTS OWNED BY THIRD PARTIES IN THE EVENT THE DEBTOR IS IN DEFAULT
- Implementation of Subrogation with Lastgeving as a Legal Instrument in the Transfer of Land Rights
- RESPONSIBILITIES OF A NOTARY IN MAKING A SUBROGATION AGREEMENT WITH GUARANTEE OF LAND RIGHTS IN BATAM CITY
- LEGAL PROTECTION FOR INSURANCE COMPANIES FOR INSURED WHO VIOLATE SUBROGATION RIGHTS
- LEGAL ASPECTS OF SUBROGATION AS A FORM OF TRANSFER OF DEPENDENT RIGHTS ACCORDING TO LAW NO. 4 OF 1996
- Implementation of the Principle of Subrogation in Motor Vehicle Insurance According to the Commercial Law Book
- SUBROGATION PRACTICES BY INSURANCE COMPANIES IN BANDUNG CITY ACCORDING TO INSURANCE LAW STUDY
- IMPLEMENTATION OF THE INSURANCE COMPANY'S SUBROGATION RIGHTS REGARDING INSURED VEHICLES
- TRANSFER OF GUARANTEES THROUGH SUBROGATION IN CREDIT AGREEMENTS ACCORDING TO LAW NUMBER 4 OF 1996

CONCERNING MONITORY RIGHTS TO LAND AND OBJECTS RELATING TO LAND

- Request for Replacement on a Subrogation Basis by PT. A As Guarantor to PT. P As Carrier and Ship Owner
- SUBROGATION AS ONE OF THE REASONS FOR VOIDING AN AGREEMENT ACCORDING TO THE CIVIL LAW BOOK (BW)
- Islamic Law Review of the Concept of Subrogation in Sharia Insurance
- THE INFLUENCE OF CLAIM RISK, REGUARANTEE, SUBROGATION AND INVESTMENT INCOME ON PROFITABILITY
- ANALYSIS OF RECORDING SUBROGATE RECEIVABLES IN GUARANTEE COMPANIES
- Implementation of Subrogation Principles in Motor Vehicle Insurance: Study at PT Pan Pacific Insurance
- FULFILLMENT OF THE RIGHTS OF PT. JAMKRIDA RIAU AS GUARANTEE IN SETTLEMENT OF PEOPLE'S BUSINESS CREDIT BY SUBROGATION
- Application of Subrogation Rights in Motor Vehicle Insurance Agreements for Losses Due to Third Party Errors
- Implementation of Subrogation Principles in Motor Vehicle Insurance: Study at PT Pan Pacific Insurance
- RESCUING PROBLEM CREDIT THROUGH SUBROGATION WITH A GUARANTEE AGENCY (Study at PT. BPR Sadhya Muktiparama, Malang Regency)
- Insurer's Subrogation Rights in Borgtocht
- JURIDICAL ANALYSIS OF SUBROGATION WITH TRANSFER OF CREDIT BOUND BY MONITORING RIGHTS TO PT. INDONESIAN PEOPLE'S BANK (PERSERO) TBK. KABANJAHE BRANCH
- SETTLEMENT OF CLAIMS AND SUBROGATION BY SURETY COMPANY AGAINST THE PRINCIPAL DEFENDER IN THE SURETY BOND AGREEMENT
- Analysis of the Use of Subrogation Deeds in the Context of Implementing Article 2 Aceh Qanun Number 11 of 2018 concerning Sharia Financial Institutions
- Settlement of Claims and Subrogation by Surety Companies in Surety Bond Agreements
- Legal Certainty of Subrogation Rights of Sharia Guarantee Companies for Financing Written Off (Write Off) by Sharia Banks (Case Study of Sharia Financing Guarantee Claims at PT Guarantee Financing Askrido Syariah)
- Assistance in Settlement of Motor Vehicle Claims Based on Subrogation Principles at PT. Tata Wahana Insurance
- Characteristics of Subrogation in Distribution of People's Business Credit from a Civil Law Perspective
- SUBROGATION RIGHTS OF INSURANCE COMPANIES IN AGREEMENTS FROM A JUSTICE PERSPECTIVE

Conclusion

Based on the results of the discussion above, it can be concluded that there are 13 mappings and 30 research topics using literature studies regarding Subrogation in Islamic and Conventional Financial Institutions.

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